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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

D6.2 Sustainability Strategy

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Nature of the deliverable:		R
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	
EU-RES	Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-CON	Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-SEC	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, stemming from WP6 "Dissemination, promotion, communication, and sustainability" and specifically task 6.4 "Development of a sustainability strategy", delineates the sustainability strategy for the StandICT.eu 2026 project and a preliminary action plan to be then executed and refined in the second part of the project. The strategy is aimed at ensuring the lasting impact and sustainability of the StandICT.eu 2026 project and the core assets developed during the current project activities, building on the achievements of the previous editions, namely StandICT.eu and StandICT.eu 2023. This is an interim version and will be updated by the end of the project with a revised deliverable D6.6 on the proposed sustainability framework.

The document starts with an introduction, encapsulating the primary objectives and establishing the context in relation to other deliverables. It then delves into the new and evolved Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that form the backbone of the project. This section provides insights into the development and enhancement of these assets during the project's third iteration, highlighting their increased potential for exploitation.

The central sections of the deliverable are dedicated to detailing the sustainability strategy of the project which consists of two main steps. The first step is the handover of the project's assets to the winning proposal of the currently open call "[A human-centred and ethical development of digital and industrial technologies \(HORIZON-CL4-2024-HUMAN-03\)](#)"

This call precisely aims to fund the successor to the current StandICT.eu initiative, as specified in the call text.

The second step entails identifying alternative sustainability models that do not solely rely on EU funding. This includes pinpointing key stakeholders, beyond consortium partners, who are interested in the initiative and could become funding partners for future phases. At this stage, a plan to engage with these entities is presented, along with a detailed interview protocol to understand their needs. This will enable the development of a value proposition for their direct involvement, thereby elaborating a business plan that could potentially strengthen the financial independence of StandICT.eu.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	Explanation
AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif, Non-Profit Organisation
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EU	European
EUOS	EU Observatory for ICT standardisation
FOREST	Forum on European Strategy for ICT Standards
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KER(s)	Key Exploitable Result(s)
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
SDO(s)	Standards Development Organisation(s)
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
TWG(s)	Technical Working Group(s)

1. INTRODUCTION

StandICT.eu 2026 is an EU Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action (CSA) that started in January 2023. Its primary objective is to ensure a neutral, reputable, pragmatic, and fair approach to bolster the presence of standardisation specialists from European and Associated states in the global ICT standardisation landscape, thereby championing European priorities. This initiative is an evolution of its successful predecessors, StandICT.eu 2023 (2020-2023) StandICT.eu (2018-2019). As StandICT.eu 2026 stands at its M18 midterm point in June 2024, this deliverable aims to highlight its significant outputs, which have matured across this and the previous two project editions.

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This deliverable delves into the planning of sustainability actions for StandICT.eu 2026. It highlights the primary Key Exploitable Results (KERs) produced by the project, which are of paramount importance to both the EC and the European ICT standards community. In addition to evaluating these actions, this document also charts the prospective direction for the project's future. The importance of these KERs is defined according to criteria such as their scalability, market potential, and strategic benefits. For example, selected KERs include the Trust-Grants™ platform, which is presenting now increased automation to reduce manual effort, the EUOS Observatory's publications and insights that can boost stakeholder engagement, and the Training Academy with the Mentorship Programme fostering knowledge transfer.

1.2 Structure

The document is divided in the following sections:

- **Introduction** – Outlining the overarching scope of the deliverable and its primary focus areas.
- **Exploitation and sustainability of project outputs** – Detailing the principal project KERs, illustrating their value and exploitation potential.
- **Transition path towards the new StandICT.eu**– Presenting the transition of the primary KERs to the subsequent to be funded StandICT.eu 2026's follow-up and guarantee continuity.
- **Longer-term sustainability roadmap** - Focussing on a strategic phased approach to fully leverage the project's KERs. The methodology and plan systematically progresses from refining the core functionalities of the KERs to securing their long-term viability setting the stage for alternative funding mechanisms to complement EC-funding.
- **Conclusions** - Summarising the key takeaways and the next steps for the implementation of the presented plan.

1.3 Relation with other project deliverables

The following StandICT.eu 2026 submitted and future deliverables are related to this document:

- D2.1 Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape
- D2.2 Stakeholder consultation process mid-term report
- D2.3 Stakeholder consultation process, final report
- D3.1 Call monitoring report no.1
- D3.2 Call monitoring report no.2
- D3.4 Call monitoring report no.4
- D4.1 Standardisation training strategy
- D4.2 Interim report on education in standardisation
- D5.1 Stakeholder engagement midterm report
- D5.2 Stakeholder engagement final report
- D5.3 Report on the interface between R&I and standardisation
- D6.1 Plan for communication & stakeholder engagement strategy & plan and promotion of the open call
- D6.4 Monitoring and contributing to sensitive issues in ICT standardisation - interim report
- D6.6 Proposed sustainability framework

2. EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1 Key Exploitable Results Overview

Ensuring the sustainability of project results begins with a foundational step, i.e. identifying and selecting the most important outcomes, the KERs. By concentrating resources on these key results, the project can efficiently channel efforts towards results presenting the highest potential for future utility and impact. KERs are indeed defined as prominent project outcomes that have been selected and prioritised due to their substantial potential for exploitation. In this context, "exploitation" refers to the ability to utilise and derive benefits from these results downstream in the value chain of a product, process, or solution. Additionally, KERs can serve as crucial inputs for policy-making, further research, or educational activities. In alignment with this definition, the project has pinpointed a series of tangible primary KERs, summarised in the table below, which are elaborated upon and in the subsequent sections. The new KERs specifically developed under the current edition of the project are highlighted in bold format.

TABLE 1 - OVERVIEW OF STANDICT.EU 2026 KERs

KER name	KER description	KER value and exploitation potential
<u>KER #1</u> <u>Trust-Grants™</u>	A custom-made grants platform used to manage open calls and related evaluations. Available since the past editions, in this iteration of the project it features increased automation and improved back-end commands to minimise manual steps.	The grants platform, refined over the project's duration, is now a benchmark tool for managing open calls. Its adaptability makes it a candidate for replication in future initiatives. This product has already been re-used by Trust-IT in other projects managing open calls
<u>KER #2</u> <u>EUOS EU Observatory for ICT standardisation</u>	An online platform, enriched from past project editions, that contains 2,851 records with information and links to official ICT standards and working groups, reflecting the latest trends and insights.	The Observatory serves as a comprehensive reference for stakeholders, increasing awareness and engagement with ICT standards across Europe.

<p>KER #3 EUOS Technical Working Groups (TWGs)</p>	<p>Groups of standardisation experts that have produced several "Landscape Analysis Reports". New reports have been added, reflecting the latest in ICT domains. Moreover two Gap Analysis Reports have been released for the first time under StandICT.eu 2026, complementing the landscapes</p>	<p>The reports provide valuable analyses and identify gaps in ICT standards, supporting informed decision-making and strategic planning. They are all freely accessible on Zenodo</p>
<p>KER #4 EUOS Standards Academy</p>	<p>A second version of the EUOS Academy is now being developed, in addition to the one developed under StandICT.eu 2023, which was kept on the website as an archive. This version contains materials directly developed by the consortium and members of the dedicated Education Group</p>	<p>The Academy offers educational resources and training, enhancing skills and knowledge in ICT standardisation</p>
<p>KER #5 Community of ICT standards organisations and standard-focused entities</p>	<p>Collaborations ensuring StandICT.eu 2026's visibility within key European organisations</p>	<p>The Community strengthens network and visibility, facilitating partnerships and increasing the initiative's influence in the ICT standardisation community.</p>
<p>KER #6 Funded Fellows</p>	<p>European experts in ICT standards who received financial support for standard-related activities.</p>	<p>Success stories and results are published in "Following the Fellows Impact Reports" on Zenodo and the website. The fellows' activities are encouraged to continue thanks to the financial support provided to experts, enhancing their continued contributions and innovations in ICT standardisation.</p>
<p>KER #7 Mentorship Programme</p>	<p>New initiative meant to support newcomers of the ICT standardisation by pairing them with more experienced professionals</p>	<p>The programme promotes knowledge transfer and skill development, ensuring a steady influx of competent professionals in ICT standardisation.</p>
<p>KER #8 Insights from ICT trends and recommendations publications</p>	<p>Set of deliverables (e.g. D2.1) and papers, available on Zenodo, to provide more detailed overviews of ICT changing drivers, trends and insights from submitted applications in specific ICT sectors</p>	<p>These publications serve as a valuable resource for understanding ICT trends and influencing future research and development directions.</p>
<p>KER #9 FOREST- Forum on European Strategy for ICT Standards</p>	<p>Group of consortium members and external experts to identify and discuss about ICT sensitive topics, also in charge to deliver a confidential report to the EC with information reported by fellows on standardisation issues</p>	<p>Informs strategic decisions with expert insights, enhancing the effectiveness of ICT standardisation initiatives.</p>

KER #10

[Insights from ICT standardisation success stories](#)

Collection of success stories from various initiatives, mostly StandICT fellows, showcasing the impact of and learnings from their standardisation efforts.

These insights demonstrate the tangible benefits and successes of ICT standardisation, encouraging adoption and continued support.

2.2 KERs detailed description

2.2.1 TRUST-GRANTS™ PLATFORM

Within WP3 / Task 3.3, led by TRUST-IT, the StandICT.eu 2026 Trust-Grants™ platform has undergone significant enhancements compared to the previous version reported at the end of StandICT.eu 2023 and described in past deliverables. Currently, the platform is able to efficiently handle peaks of over 100 applications per call on average. It also features improvements in executing routine tasks that were previously more manual, such as assigning evaluators, downloading score dumps per application, and visualising detailed information, with additional filters, including data about applications previously submitted by the same applicant. Comprehensive details about the latest updates to the Trust-Grants™ platform will be included in the D3.2 Call Monitoring Report No. 2, due in July 2024.

FIGURE 1 - SELECTED VIEWS OF THE GRANTS PLATFORM FILTERING AND VISUALISATION OPTIONS

2.2.2 EUOS EU OBSERVATORY FOR ICT STANDARDISATION

The EU Observatory for ICT Standards (EUOS) Repository is a comprehensive online platform designed to house an extensive collection of information to ICT standards and related resources. As of June 2024, the Repository contains links to more than 2,800 standards and working groups, significantly expanded from previous editions. It serves as a crucial reference for stakeholders by offering detailed information on standards, links to official documents, and

insights into ongoing developments in various ICT domains such as AI, blockchain, cybersecurity, smart cities, and more. The platform also acts as an engagement channel for the ICT standardisation community through its discussion groups, which facilitate collaboration among standardisation experts, EU research projects, and other stakeholders. These groups are instrumental in sharing achievements, discussing emerging trends, and reinforcing collaborations across the ICT standardisation landscape. By continually updating its content, the EUOS ensures that the latest technological advancements and expert insights are readily accessible to its users, thereby fostering innovation and alignment with the European market.

FIGURE 2 - SELECTED VISUALS AND STATISTICS OF THE EUOS OBSERVATORY

2.2.3 EUOS TECHNICAL WORKING GROUPS (TWGS)

The Technical Working Groups (TWGs) within the StandICT.eu initiative play a pivotal role in advancing ICT standardisation efforts. These groups consist of senior experts from various Standards Development Organisations (SDOs) operating globally. The TWGs are tasked with creating detailed reports, responding to EC-relevant ICT topics and priorities. Each TWG operates with a dedicated Chair to provide clear guidance and leadership. The topics covered by the TWGs are diverse, ranging from digital twins and artificial intelligence to edge computing, internet of things, smart cities, and trusted information. These groups have already produced several reports, including both landscape and gap analysis reports, which help identify key areas for standardisation and inform strategic decision-making. The new landscape reports released by StandICT.eu 2026 are:

- [Standardisation landscape for citiverse](#)
- [Landscape of ontologies standards](#)
- [Landscape of digital product passport standards](#)

The new gap analysis reports released by StandICT.eu 2026 for the first time are:

- [Edge computing standardisation gaps](#)
- [IoT standardisation gaps](#)

The collaborative efforts of the TWGs ensure that the EUOS remains a reference platform for ICT standardisation insights.

Discover the reports

FIGURE 3 - SAMPLE OF PUBLISHED TWG LANDSCAPE AND GAP ANALYSIS REPORTS

2.2.4 EUOS STANDARDS ACADEMY

The [StandICT.eu EUOS Standards Academy](#), already launched in StandICT.eu 2023, has transformed under the 2026 edition, enhancing its role in promoting ICT standardisation education. The revamped platform features a cleaner, more intuitive design and streamlined navigation, making it easier for users to find training modules suited to their needs and knowledge levels. The new Academy offers expanded content, including archived materials from StandICT.eu 2023 and new modules authored by experts in the field. The updated platform also introduces dedicated training webinars on key topics like Geopolitics of ICT standardisation and the Standards Essential Patent regulation. The content of the Academy is curated by an ad hoc Standards Education Group guided by Knut Blind, StandICT.eu partner and Ivana Mijatovic, [HSbooster.eu](#) partner. The content of the Academy has also been recently featured amongst the teaching repository of the new EU project [EDU4Standards.eu](#), reference point for Education in Standardisation, to enhance its visibility, exploitation and re-use by other communities. More details are available in D4.1 – Standardisation Training Strategy and D4.2 – Interim report on Education in Standardisation.

FIGURE 4 - SELECTED VISUALS OF THE STANDICT.EU 2026 TRAINING ACADEMY

2.2.5 COMMUNITY OF ICT STANDARDS ORGANISATIONS AND STANDARD-FOCUSED ENTITIES

StandICT.eu 2023 has developed and nurtured a series of collaborations in the form of Memorandum of Understanding(s) (MoUs) or cross-project collaborations to ensure optimal visibility of the StandICT.eu 2026 initiative within key European projects, organisations and associations contributing to international ICT standardisation. At its mid-term, the project has signed 22 memorandum of understanding with relevant stakeholders announced with joint press releases¹.

The primary goal has been to establish a diverse, vast and influential network through strategic synergies with ongoing initiatives both at European and global level, in order to secure and tap into the wide range of competencies and skills needed to provide the required international breadth to the Project. This is pursued through the wide range of activities aiming to achieve the following outputs:

¹ <https://www.standict.eu/news>

- **Concrete involvement and ongoing coordination with Regional and International SDOs** with the objective of promoting the opportunities offered by the Open Calls among the relative ICT Communities, disseminating the impact attained through the work carried out by the funded experts and TWGs, identifying and highlighting arising topics and/or challenges requiring further research and policy inputs, to be timely included in the Open Calls priority list.
- **Enduring and reciprocal cooperation with National Standard Bodies** to obtain a complete mapping of the different national perspectives and steer ICT Policy development towards a more Eurocentric approach.
- **Synergies with similar initiatives including European (and national) funded** projects with standardisation-focused tasks or effort. Further details on these synergies and collaborative efforts are reported in D5.1 – Stakeholder engagement midterm report, which was submitted in M17 – May 2024.

2.2.6 FUNDED FELLOWS

At the time of writing, the project has successfully launched a total of five Open Calls, of which the first four have led to the funding of 147 applications for a total of approximately 1.3 million Euros out of the 3 million Euros earmarked for Financial Support to Third Parties.

The most tangible outputs and research outputs of those individuals have been summarised in a series of dedicated publications, called “[Following the Fellows Impact Reports](#)”, which highlight a variety of evidence-based outcomes gained through the project’s open calls. The reports put the fellows themselves, namely those individuals who have successfully won an application in the StandICT.eu 2026 open calls, under the spotlight and offer them the opportunity to speak about their work and the added-value they are contributing to standards efforts as awardees from their own perspectives. Showcasing the most important and significant outcomes to date, the StandICT.eu 2026 fellows share not only the results garnered, but importantly they also highlight the impact of these results. The “Following the Fellows” reports are available in a dedicated area of the website.²

Moreover a new webpage highlighting the fellows and their activities has been released as part of the M16 website revamp³

² The section is available [here](#)

³ The new webpage is available [here](#)

StandICT.eu Fellows

Welcome to the StandICT.eu Fellows page, where you can discover the talented ICT standardisation experts funded through the StandICT.eu 2026 open calls. Delve into their profiles to explore their diverse expertise and contributions to advancing ICT standardisation activities. The StandICT.eu fellows play a crucial role in shaping the future of ICT standards at European and global levels, bringing their perspectives and insights to the forefront. Learn more about their valuable contributions to the standardisation landscape.

Year of application

2023
 2024

Topic

KEY ENABLERS

- 5G and Beyond (6G)
- Cloud and Edge Computing
- Big Data & Open data
- IoT Internet of Things
- Broadband infrastructure mapping
- Accessibility of ICT products and services
- Artificial Intelligence
- Quantum Technologies

FOUNDATIONAL DRIVERS

- Cybersecurity/Network and Information security
- E-Privacy

INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET

- Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies

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1st Open Call
2nd Open Call

Adam Smith
Spain
Artificial Intelligence
1st Open Call

Agnieszka Rządtkowska
Belgium
Artificial Intelligence
1st Open Call

Alessio Tartaro
Italy
Artificial Intelligence
1st Open Call

FIGURE 5 - OVERVIEW OF THE WEBPAGE DEDICATED TO STANDICT FUNDED FELLOWS

2.2.7 MENTORSHIP PROGRAMME

The StandICT.eu [Mentorship Programme](#) is a new initiative of the 2026 edition, dedicated to fostering a new generation of European standardisation experts. This one-to-one mentorship initiative aims to support SME newcomers with less experience in SDO technical committees by pairing them with seasoned experts. The experienced fellows provide valuable tips, advice, and guidance, thereby diffusing their extensive knowledge to new professionals. This contributes to maintaining a robust standardisation knowledge base for the future within the European Union. Mentorship can take various forms, including direct exchanges, sharing resources, or inviting mentees to relevant meetings and conferences. This flexible approach allows mentors to tailor their support based on the mentees' specific needs and goals. To facilitate this, a new question has been added to the general open call application form, asking applicants if they are interested in participating in the mentorship programme as either a mentor or a mentee. The StandICT.eu team matches interested fellows from each open call based on similar expertise areas and monitors the mentoring process. A feedback session is organised at the end of the fellowship to review experiences and make necessary adjustments for future cycles. The programme has been opened for applications during the fourth open call of the StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme, and the kick-off of the initiative is scheduled to take place on 3rd July 2024.

2.2.8 INSIGHTS FROM ICT TRENDS AND RECOMMENDATIONS PUBLICATIONS

StandICT.eu has been at the forefront of monitoring and analysing ICT trends and providing valuable recommendations through various publications. One of the key deliverables is D2.1, titled "Europe's Place in a Changing ICT Standardisation Landscape," released in April 2024 (M16). This comprehensive report outlines Europe's strategic positioning and contributions to the evolving ICT standardisation ecosystem, offering critical insights and forward-looking recommendations. In addition to D2.1, [an earlier report of recommendations](#) provided essential guidance for stakeholders involved in ICT standardisation. These efforts are set to continue with dedicated case studies focusing on transversal topics, ensuring ongoing relevance and support for the European ICT community.

Furthermore, StandICT.eu has initiated the publication of short conference papers addressing current ICT trends. A notable example is a paper on 5G trends, which was presented at the EURAS conference in June 2024 (M18). At the moment of writing this deliverable, proceedings are being processed by the organisers of the conference and will be available online soon. This paper highlights the characteristics and aggregated statistics of applications received by StandICT.eu in the 5G domain, contributing to the broader activities on ICT standardisation. Other papers on different ICT fields are planned for the future. These publications serve as resources for understanding the dynamics of ICT trends and provide actionable recommendations to support Europe's leadership in the global standardisation landscape.

2.2.9 FOREST- FORUM ON EUROPEAN STRATEGY FOR ICT STANDARDS

StandICT.eu has setup a dedicated board named FOREST in its 2026 edition. This body aims to highlight sensitive issues around ICT standardisation also via the organisation of dedicated events. Notable examples of initiatives organised under FOREST are the second and third event of the "women in ICT standardisation" series, started already under StandICT.eu 2023 and the webinar on Human Rights and ICT standardisation co-organised with HSbooster.eu on 6th June 2024⁴. This body also provides an important service to the EC reporting in confidential form signalling early warnings on behaviours in SDOs that may contrast EU values. More details on the FOREST activities and value are reported in D6.4 submitted concurrently to this deliverable.

2.2.10 INSIGHTS FROM ICT STANDARDISATION SUCCESS STORIES

In continuation of the activities started under the StandICT.eu 2023 project, StandICT.eu 2026 is continuing the curation of a [collection of success stories](#) that span beyond the boundaries of our project, capturing the essence of standardisation excellence from various fields of the ICT

⁴ Further details are available online: https://www.standict.eu/events_and_in_Deliverable_D6.4 submitted simultaneously to the present document

domain. These examples, accessible on the StandICT.eu platform, describe the significant strides made by experts, both from within our fellows and from other initiatives.

The success stories so far collected, while rooted in individual or collective achievements, represent a broader vision of what is possible in the realm of ICT standardisation. They are a testament to the collaborative spirit of the community and the impact of standardisation efforts, making them a key exploitable asset for the StandICT.eu initiative and beyond.

2.3 KER analysis: strengths, risks and mitigation measures

The collective strengths of the StandICT.eu 2026 KERs are rooted in their comprehensive and synergistic approach to advancing ICT standardisation across Europe. In summary, the project is able to efficiently manage grant applications, provide a vast and continually updated repository of ICT standards, facilitate expert collaboration through dedicated technical working groups, and promote robust educational and mentorship initiatives. These results collectively foster innovation, streamline operational processes, and ensure a well-informed, skilled workforce, contributing to the enhancement of Europe's leadership in global ICT standardisation.

However, there are potential risks that must be considered. Technological obsolescence is a major concern, as rapid advancements can quickly render existing resources outdated. This risk can be mitigated by ensuring regular updates and maintaining a dynamic approach to incorporating the latest technological trends and developments. Another risk is fluctuating stakeholder engagement, which can undermine the project's collaborative efforts. To address this, active and inclusive communication strategies are employed, ensuring continuous and meaningful engagement from all stakeholders. Additionally, effective knowledge transfer within the Mentorship Programme can be challenging, especially in ensuring both mentors and mentees are committed and productive. Structured feedback mechanisms and ongoing monitoring can help mitigate this risk, ensuring that knowledge transfer is efficient and impactful.

By proactively addressing these risks through these mitigation strategies, StandICT.eu 2026 can sustain and enhance its impact, ensuring continued leadership in ICT standardisation efforts.

3. TRANSITION PATH TOWARDS THE NEW STANDICT.EU

As the StandICT.eu 2026 project approaches its second and final stage, a critical focus is the transition of its assets to the forthcoming edition of StandICT.eu which will be awarded as an outcome of the selection procedure published on the EU portal for the call "[A human-centred and ethical development of digital and industrial technologies \(HORIZON-CL4-2024-HUMAN-03\)](#)" with a deadline in September 2024. This transition is essential for ensuring the continuity and sustainability of the project's significant achievements in ICT standardisation. Given the uncertainty about whether the current consortium will continue or if a different team will take over, it is crucial to evaluate various scenarios and establish a robust transition strategy. In particular two scenarios are possible:

- **Scenario 1 - Current consortium continues:** If the current consortium is awarded the next edition, the transition process allow for a seamless continuation of the established processes and initiatives, leveraging the existing team's familiarity and expertise.
- **Scenario 2 - Different consortium takes over:** In the event a new consortium is awarded the project, a comprehensive knowledge transfer plan is essential. This includes, where necessary, providing documentation about assets, processes, and guidelines to ensure most of the assets are preserved. Of course, such strategy depends on the characteristics of the new awarded project and the main current assets it wishes to bring forward in the new iteration of the initiative.

It is evident that scenario 1 would be the easiest for the consortium to manage and will imply a seamless continuation and enrichment of all ongoing activities and assets. Scenario 2, instead, brings up a few challenges and risks which are listed below:

- **Asset management and handover:** The Trust-Grants™ platform, the EUOS Repository, the Standards Academy and all the technological assets need to be maintained, updated, and possibly enhanced. If these platforms are also envisioned in the new funded proposal, an agreement should be found regarding their future and ownership roles. Ensuring these tools are well-documented and the new team has access to user manuals, and support contacts. The current StandICT.eu 2026 consortium shall organise an handover meeting and plan with the future funded consortium to agree on all relevant aspects. Regarding community-related assets, the relationships and networks built with stakeholders, including technical working groups, funded fellows, and standardisation organisations, must be carefully transitioned. This involves introducing the new team to key contacts and ensuring ongoing communication channels remain open and active to make sure the work done so far is leveraged in an optimal way.
- **Continuity risk management and mitigation:** The primary risk in transitioning to a new consortium is the potential loss of momentum and continuity for the work done over several years. Mitigation measures include detailed transition plans, phased handover periods which need to be agreed with the future consortium. A joint team to monitor and execute the transition shall be put in place. By thoroughly preparing for both scenarios, the StandICT.eu initiative can ensure that its valuable assets and achievements are effectively transitioned to the next edition, maintaining its impact and leadership in the field of ICT standardisation.

4. LONGER-TERM SUSTAINABILITY ROADMAP

As we already know, the shorter term sustainability for StandICT.eu will be guaranteed by the StandICT.eu 2026's follow-up project which will be selected and progress for a few years after 2026. However, additional actions will be needed to maximise the results' exploitation potential and the sustainability of the initiative in the longer term, after the awarded follow-up concludes. At this stage in time, we have set up a plan with a phased approach to be able to concretely provide sustainability options that go beyond the continuous funding of follow-up proposals. In the past StandICT.eu 2023 deliverables, we mentioned the idea to convert StandICT.eu into an AISBL (Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif), a non-for-profit organisation that would sign service agreements with any national, EU, international and private initiatives working on ICT standardisation to guarantee the funding scheme continues. At the StandICT.eu 2023 final review in October 2023, the consortium was specifically asked to elaborate more on this option. The following paragraphs therefore present our plan of action for this case. The establishment of an AISBL to continue the activities of StandICT, either independently or in conjunction with additional EU funding, requires a strategic and phased approach, which also serves to understand whether pursuing an AISBL is truly the optimal path or if other viable and more appropriate alternatives might emerge.

Below is a preliminary action plan divided into phases, each with specific tasks. Being the sustainability task a transversal one, some of these activities have been or will be conducted in synergy with other tasks across all the project Work Packages.

4.1 Phase 1- Initial Analysis and Stakeholder Identification

The first phase (2023 and 2024) focuses on identifying potential stakeholders and understanding their needs to build a solid foundation for the AISBL. The process begins with mapping key stakeholders, including industry experts, academic institutions, SDOs, SMEs, and governmental bodies, and compiling a detailed database of their contact information and roles in ICT standardisation. This mapping activity is performed as part of WP5 which is responsible for maintaining the project database. Each KER has specific target stakeholders that could value that asset the most, e.g. the Academy is most interesting for academia and research, while the EUOS repository is most interesting for ICT standards experts.

Brainstorming sessions were held with the consortium to identify the highest-potential stakeholders to involve more concretely in the StandICT.eu initiative and SDOs (at National, European and International level) have been selected as the most transversal and possibly interested in the continuation of this project's activities given that the majority of its budget is used to allow experts work for the SDOs. The experts' effort would be more limited and voluntary-based only, if StandICT.eu was not in place. A second category of interesting stakeholders lies in the other standards-focussed EU-funded projects that may have synergistic outputs or be interested in a joint exploitation of some of StandICT.eu consolidated assets (e.g., [Seeblocks.eu](https://www.seeblocks.eu), [Stand4EU](https://www.stand4eu.eu), [Blockstand](https://www.blockstand.eu), [HSbooster.eu](https://www.hsbooster.eu), [EDU4Standards.eu](https://www.edu4standards.eu), [Cyberstand.eu](https://www.cyberstand.eu), [Indico-Global](https://www.indico-global.com), [INSTAR](https://www.instar.eu), among others).

T5.2 - R&I project synergies is in charge of synergies with these projects and many relevant events and publications have been made already with them, as detailed in deliverable D5.1. The partners of these projects' consortia, that partially overlap across different projects, are

identified as another interesting and primary stakeholder category to involve in this initial analysis.

To gain insights into these stakeholders' needs, surveys and interviews will need to be conducted relying on a standardised interview protocol. This will help in gathering comprehensive data on their expectations and challenges. The collected data will be analysed to identify common themes, which will inform the development of a preliminary value proposition that aligns with the stakeholders' needs and leverages the strengths of StandICT.eu's KERs. As part of the activities for this phase an interview protocol has been established and it is available in Appendix 1 – Interviews will be conducted in the coming months and until the end of 2024. Additional stakeholder categories may be interviewed in a second step. This activity will be crucial in developing preliminary insights, which will then be subject to a broader stakeholder consultation process, the second for the StandICT.eu 2026 project. The outcomes and results from this consultation, described in D2.3 – Stakeholder consultation process final report will be integrated into the final version of deliverable D6.6 – Proposed sustainability framework.

4.2 Phase 2 - Detailed planning

In the second phase (2025), the focus shifts to developing a detailed business plan in preparation for the potential forming of the AISBL legal entity or an alternative initiative. A comprehensive business model will be outlined, covering the mission, vision, objectives, governance structure, funding mechanisms, and operational plans, based on the results of phase 1, including the stakeholder consultation process. This plan will identify potential revenue streams such as membership fees and service fees. This will be delivered as part of StandICT.eu 2026 and included in the final D6.6 which will update the present deliverable

4.2 Phase 3 – Operational setup, pilot and implementation

In the third phase (2026-2028) the StandICT.eu 2026's follow-up will presumably start. Based on whether the present or a different consortium will be awarded, the activities implemented and the structure of this final phase could differ significantly. In the hypothesis the current consortium survives or the new consortium agrees with the plan defined as an outcome of phase 2, this phase could see the formation of the AISBL under Belgian law or an alternative institution, in the hypothesis the project is not further funded by the EC solely. If this scenario materialises, the statutes and bylaws will be drafted and approved, and the AISBL will be registered with relevant authorities. During this phase, the business plan and value proposition will be presented to key stakeholders to secure their support and commitment. Founding members and partners will be identified, and a founding committee will be established to oversee initial operations which will work as a pilot to identify success factors and elements that need improvement. The range of assets and services may be then expanded based on learnings from the pilot phase to make sure that membership will be increased, and the stakeholder base broadened through marketing and outreach campaigns.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Building on the two previous editions, the StandICT.eu 2026 project has so far made significant progress in enhancing the landscape of ICT standardisation through its comprehensive initiatives and KERs. Overall, StandICT.eu 2026 has identified 10 KERs, 3 of which are a novelty of this edition. Aggregated, these results build a solid base for the sustainable exploitation plan of StandICT.eu. To present these results, this deliverable has detailed the achievements across various work packages and project tasks, emphasising the development and optimisation of key assets such as the Trust-Grants™ platform, the EUOS Repository, the Standards Academy, and the newly launched initiatives such as the mentorship programme and new detailed reports and publications. Each of these components has played a crucial role in supporting ICT standardisation efforts, fostering innovation, and building a robust community of experts. They also form the foundation for the exploitation and sustainability strategy outlined in chapters 3 and 4 of this deliverable. This strategy delineates various phases and scenarios for potentially transitioning to an AISBL, including plans for stakeholder engagement, interviews with potential partners and a broader stakeholder consultation process to be run in the second part of the project. By leveraging these well-developed assets and strategic plans, StandICT.eu 2026 is well-positioned to ensure the continuity, impact and growth of its standardisation activities.

APPENDIX – INTERVIEW PROTOCOL FOR SDOS AND PARTNERS OF STANDARDS-RELATED EU PROJECTS

To effectively gather insights from both SDOs and other standards-oriented EU-funded projects, primary stakeholders identified as potential contributors to a longer-term StandICT.eu initiative, tailored questions are necessary. This appendix contains the prepared questions for the interviews. Some questions will be suitable for both types of stakeholders, while others will be specific to SDOs or project partners. This approach ensures comprehensive and relevant data collection.

Interview protocol

Introduction (Interviewer – StandICT.eu)

- Introduce yourself and provide a brief overview of the StandICT.eu initiative and its goals.
- Explain the purpose of the interview and assure confidentiality.
- Request permission to record the interview for accuracy in data collection.

Background Information (for both SDOs and Project Partners):

Organisational Role and Involvement

- Can you provide an overview of your organisation's role in ICT standardisation?
- What specific areas of ICT standardisation does your organisation focus on?
- How long has your organisation been involved in ICT standardisation activities?

Current Engagement and Contributions

- What are the key projects or initiatives your organisation is currently involved in related to ICT standards?
- How do you typically contribute to these standards (e.g., developing new standards, participating in working groups)?
- Can you share any significant achievements or contributions your organisation has made in the field of ICT standardisation?

Needs and Challenges (for both SDOs and Project Partners):

Resource and Support Needs

- What types of resources or support does your organisation currently utilise for ICT standardisation?
- Are there specific resources or support mechanisms that you find lacking or insufficient?
- How do you think StandICT.eu can enhance its offerings to better support your standardisation activities?

Challenges in Standardisation

- What are the biggest challenges your organisation faces in ICT standardisation?
- How do these challenges impact your ability to develop or implement standards effectively?
- Have there been any recent changes or trends in the ICT standardisation landscape that have introduced new challenges?

Perception and Interaction with StandICT.eu (for both SDOs and Project Partners):

Experience with StandICT.eu

- How familiar are you with the resources and initiatives provided by StandICT.eu?
- Have you or your organisation participated in any StandICT.eu programs or used its resources? If so, please describe your experience.
- What aspects of StandICT.eu's offerings have been most beneficial to your work?

Improvements and expectations

- Are there any areas where you feel StandICT.eu could improve its support or resources?
- What additional services or programs would you like to see from StandICT.eu?
- How can StandICT.eu better facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing among ICT standardisation stakeholders?

Future Collaboration and Value Proposition (for SDOs and project partners):

Interest in Continued Collaboration

- How interested would your organisation be in collaborating with StandICT.eu in the future?
- Are there specific areas or projects where you see potential for deeper collaboration?

Value Proposition Development

- What value do you see in the continuation of StandICT.eu's activities through an AISBL?
- What key benefits would your organisation expect from being involved in such an association?
- Are there any specific conditions or requirements that would make your organisation more likely to engage with the AISBL?

Key Exploitable Results (for project partners)

- What are the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) from your project?
- How do you see these KERs synergising with those of StandICT.eu?
- Are there specific areas or projects where you see potential for deeper collaboration?

Closing (for both SDOs and project partners):

Additional Comments

- Do you have any additional comments or suggestions regarding StandICT.eu or the proposed AISBL?
- Are there other stakeholders or organisations you believe we should engage with during this process?

Thank You (Interviewer – StandICT.eu)

Thank the interviewee for their time and valuable insights.

Inform them about the next steps and how their feedback will be used in the StandICT.eu sustainability plan